

Effect of Nepotism on Productivity among Public Servants in Nigeria

OKORO PRINCE NKEMAKOLAM
FACULTY OF BUSINESS AND ECONOMICS
UNIVERSITI MALAYA
KUALA LUMPUR

TABLE OF CONTENT

TABLE OF CONTENT	1919
ABSTRACT	1920
CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION	1921
<i>A. Background of The Study</i>	1921
<i>B. Justification of The Study</i>	1921
<i>C. Statement of Problem</i>	1921
<i>D. Research Questions</i>	1922
<i>E. Study Aims and Objectives</i>	1922
<i>F. Research Hypothesis</i>	1923
CHAPTER TWO: Literature Review	1924
<i>A. Introduction</i>	1924
<i>B. Conceptual Framework</i>	1924
<i>C. Theoretical Framework</i>	1925
<i>D. Empirical Review</i>	1926
CHAPTER THREE: Methodology	1927
<i>A. Introduction</i>	1927
<i>B. Research Method</i>	1927
<i>C. Research Philosophy</i>	1927
<i>D. Research Design</i>	1927
<i>E. Sampling Technique</i>	1927
<i>F. Data Collection Method</i>	1927
<i>G. Data Analysis Method</i>	1927
<i>H. Ethical Consideration</i>	1928
CHAPTER FOUR: Result	1929
<i>A. Introduction</i>	1929
<i>B. Reliability Statistics</i>	1929
<i>C. Data Presentation and Analysis</i>	1929
<i>D. Hypothesis Testing</i>	1936
CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION	1939
<i>A. Introduction</i>	1939
<i>B. Summary of Analysis</i>	1939
CHAPTER SIX: CONCLUSION	1940
REFERENCES	1941

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to investigate the impact of nepotism on the productivity of public servants within Nigeria's public sector, with specific objectives including the examination of nepotism's effects on productivity, analysis of favouritism's influence on productivity, exploration of cronyism's impact on productivity, and assessment of the relationship between close network ties and effective teamwork in administrative policy. Employing a quantitative research design, data collection involved the administration of a questionnaire featuring closed-ended questions distributed via an online survey using Google Forms. Hypotheses were tested through Pearson correlation coefficient analysis. The findings indicated a positive correlation between nepotism and productivity, as well as between favouritism and productivity within Nigeria's public sector. Additionally, a weak positive correlation was observed between cronyism and productivity, alongside a similar correlation between close network ties and effective teamwork in administrative policy. The research concluded that nepotism significantly influences public servants' productivity within Nigeria's public sector. Recommendations stemming from these findings include the establishment of transparent recruiting and promotion procedures grounded in merit and qualifications, the provision of comprehensive training and development opportunities for all employees, and promotion of diversity and inclusion in the workplace to mitigate nepotism and foster fairness.

CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

A. *Background of the Study*

In the majority of nations, the public sector is tasked with providing the general public with critical services through institutions run by government departments, agencies, and ministries (Uche et al. 2019). According to Alabi and Sakariyau (2013) and Kinyua (2012), government agencies are among the largest employers of employment, therefore the competence and efficacy of public institutions are essential to the success of countries. Nepotism can easily be allowed to take place in the hiring, promotion, and training procedures in the management of public institutions, which is in contrast to the ownership and management of private sector businesses in many countries (such as Nigeria). Compromises in human resource management practices make nepotism easily tolerable (Nyukorong, 2014).

There is a common misperception that recruiting decisions within the public sector are more usually based on favouritism and nepotism than on the necessary skills, expertise, or physical health. The intended audience for the job listings is the people who interact often with these organisations. The public sector is vulnerable to a lot of internal and external pressure as well as bias when it comes to filling job opportunities (Uche et al., 2019). The top management is under pressure from the political elite and their friends and relatives. Due to pressure and bias, standards for competence, eligibility, knowledge, and suitability are ignored throughout the employment process (Paais & Pattiruhu, 2020).

According to Elbaz, Haddoud, and Shehawy (2018), the prevalence of nepotism in human resource practises is a problem that can be traced back to the diversity of racial and ethnic groups, religious affiliations, and strong familial ties (Firfiray, Cruz, Neacsu, & Gomez-Mejia, 2018). Worldwide, nepotism affects a variety of organisations, not just those in the public and private sectors (Gjinovci, 2016). Nepotism is a strategy employed to uphold family relationships at the expense of the productivity and skill of workers hired by for-profit businesses. When it comes to performance and quality, nepotism almost always brings disappointing outcomes. They most certainly lack the qualifications for the jobs that friends, family, or people with political clout are expected to occupy. During trying times, they frequently receive favours, advancements, or protection. This impairs workplace performance and productivity as well as leadership. While family members gain from nepotism, it harms those who oversee or work for the unrelated recipients. The workers' perception that there is no fairness in the workplace is impacted by this circumstance. As a result, a lack of confidence affects enthusiasm, efficiency, and satisfaction with work (Büte and Tekarslan, 2010). Nepotism, cronyism, and favouritism are on the rise inside the public sector, relative to the private sector (Shabbir & Siddique, 2017). The key enabler of nepotism, cronyism, and favouritism in these businesses is upper management. Favouritism often appears everywhere and, in most organisations, (Ozler & Buyukarslan, 2011). When a competent individual is not hired due to personal bias, this practice is known as favouritism (Kwon, 2006). Yet, nepotism must lead to a decline in organisational performance (Shabbir & Siddique, 2017). Favouritism, nepotism, and cronyism are the primary causes of employee dissatisfaction in any organisation (Ozler & Buyukarslan, 2011). The argument is made in earlier literature that favouritism, nepotism, and cronyism have an impact on employee careers and organisational success.

B. *Justification of the Study*

Nepotism, cronyism, and favouritism have all received criticism for allegedly being unethical (Abdalla, Magharabi & Raggad, 1998). Although wealthy countries have laws against preferential treatment, these practices are nevertheless widespread in developing countries (Boadi, 2000). Significantly preferentially treated organisations are unable to manage their human resources divisions independently. As a result, obtaining appointments based on the acquisition of skills and knowledge would seem unachievable under these circumstances. If an employee is up against someone with privilege, they have a very slim probability of earning the promotion. The research presented here aims to comprehend how nepotism affects public servants' productivity in Nigeria's public sectors. There is a dearth of empirical information on the connection between nepotism and worker productivity in the public sector, regardless of the actuality that research has examined nepotism with its effect on organisational outcome variables with ambiguous results. Considering the foregoing, this study is vital to collect empirical information on the impact of nepotistic practices on employees' productivity, particularly in the setting of Nigeria, where political intrigue permeates every aspect of life.

C. *Statement of Problem*

The term "nepotism" raises doubts because the word is filled with subtleties and concealed meanings, it describes the interaction of organisational politics that results in a person's appointment to a role primarily because of their relatedness (i.e., familial ties, or lineage) (Bute, 2011). One of the issues facing modern firm management is the use of nepotism, which frequently disregards the requirements for experience, professional expertise and mindset. Instead of using the merit-based reference, nepotism focuses mostly on organisational political activity (Yasir et al., 2013). Particularly in the current system of political patronage, nepotism has merged with the undesired culture that is being displaced daily. The practice of giving preferential treatment to kins of institution owners or administrators is known as nepotism, which is a kind of corruption. According to some, the public sector has devolved into a haven for nepotism as a result of poor institutional governance, with spouses, aunts, cousins, and brothers of top management employees being hired to fill key posts regardless of their qualifications. Merit-based hiring and evaluation therefore seem unlikely in such a situation. The detrimental impact of nepotism on employee productivity in the public sector cannot be

overstated because it undermines meritocracy, reduces job satisfaction, and demoralises the workforce. The high level of favouritism in appointments, promotions, and resource allocation based solely on family or personal connections fosters a toxic work environment that limits the potential of qualified employees and denies the general public services that could improve their well-being. Additionally, nepotism within the public sector promotes corruption, which negatively affects the economy of the entire nation. The prevalence of corruption within the public sector rises as an outcome of those who are appointed based on their connections feeling compelled to their supporters and frequently engaging in dishonest behaviour to repay them. To achieve sustainable development in the administration of publicly held institutions, cutting-edge human resource practices that are opposed to the ideals of fairness, justice, and equity must be checked (James, 2018).

Legislative measures are used to prevent nepotistic behaviour in developed countries; however, despite these measures' benefits to those nations, nepotistic behaviour persists frequently in the everyday operations of the business environment in developing countries because the policies against such behaviour are not implemented there (Boadi, 2000; Arasli et al., 2006).

There has been a delay in studies on how nepotism impacts the effective operation of public sectors in terms of organisational performance and ethical competence, although research on issues of corruption, nepotism, and godfatherism in most management is expanding.

Despite efforts to improve worker productivity, the prevalence of nepotism in Nigeria's government sectors continues to cause concern. Therefore, it could be essential to comprehend how nepotism impacts productivity in Nigeria's public sectors to create efficient policies and procedures to address the issue and optimise these sectors' productivity potential. The negative effects of nepotism on employee output in Nigeria's public sectors highlight a serious issue that affects such sectors. Nepotism is a pervasive practice in Nigeria's public sector, where people are routinely appointed based on their political affiliations, family ties, and personal connections rather than their qualifications and performance. Nepotism's negative effects on employee productivity in Nigeria's public sectors highlight a pressing problem that necessitates immediate government action to address. To improve Nigeria's public sector's productivity and performance, the government must combat corruption, increase transparency, and promote meritocracy in the selection of public officials.

In Nigeria, most government officials use their positions to assist others who are close to them even when they are unqualified for the position. Due to nepotism, hiring and promotion decisions are no longer primarily based on merit, and inexperienced and inept people are regularly appointed to positions of leadership. Such people might not have the skills required to perform the work properly if they are hired for positions requiring specific training and knowledge. This could lead to inefficiency, poor decision-making, and a lack of responsibility and may compromise the standards of public service. In the public sector, job interviews and other selection criteria are compromised to ensure that the preferred candidate is appointed, to the actual performance of the job, and the merit-based hiring and promotion system is eliminated due to nepotism. In this process, the nepotistic relationship is exploited to engage in unethical behaviour like embezzlement and bribery, this can occur at various levels of government. These corrupt practices can have detrimental effects on society as a whole, including the loss of public finances/monies, the decline in public trust in public institutions, the incapacity of governmental organisations to successfully carry out their mandates, and underqualified people who commonly hold positions of authority. As a result, the standard of service is frequently subpar, which undermines public administration's trustworthiness. Governments therefore must combat nepotism and guarantee that public appointments are made based on qualifications and merit rather than personal connections.

D. Research Questions

➤ *The Study will Address the Following Research Questions;*

- What is the effect of nepotism on the productivity of public servants in Nigeria's public sector?
- Why is there an effect of favouritism on the productivity of public servants in Nigeria's public sector?
- How does cronyism affect the productivity of public servants in the public sector in Nigeria?
- How do close network ties produce effective teamwork in administrative policy?

E. Study Aims and Objectives

This study aims to analyse the effect of nepotism on the productivity of public servants within Nigeria's public sector. The specific objectives are;

- To examine the effect of nepotism on the productivity of public servants in Nigeria's public sector.
- To analyse the effect of favouritism on public servants' productivity in Nigeria's public sector.
- To investigate the effect of cronyism on public servants' productivity in Nigeria's public sector.
- To examine if close network ties produce effective teamwork in administrative policy.

F. Research Hypothesis

➤ *The following Hypotheses in the Research Include:*

- H1: There is no significant relationship between nepotism and the productivity of public servants in Nigeria's public sector.
- H2: There is no significant relationship between favouritism and public servants' productivity in Nigeria's public sector.
- H3: There is no significant relationship between cronyism and public servants' productivity in Nigeria's public sector.
- H4: There is no significant relationship between close network ties and effective teamwork in administrative policy

CHAPTER TWO LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Introduction

This section critically examines the concepts, the theories and the empirical review of past findings. It explains the key concept in the research topic, the theories relating to the study and the gap statement in the study.

B. Conceptual Framework

➤ *Nepotism*

The word nepotism has a negative connotation. When a position in a company is passed down to a person's family or relatives without any interviewing or screening, this is known as nepotism. (Fisman, 2017). Nepotism is the technique of offering members of one's family preferential treatment, usually through employment (Rimvydas and Ieva, 2020). When ties are more important than credentials, competencies, abilities, and experience, nepotism is present and it has an impact on both employee and organisational success (Nadeem, Ahmad, Ahmad, Batoo, & Shafique, 2015).

However, when talented employees find out about nepotism, they become unmotivated, their performance falls short of expectations, and the majority of employees abandon their jobs; as a result, the turnover ratio in these organisations is exceptionally high (Aldossari & Bourne, 2016). According to Breuer (2010), the workplace has developed for years to represent the diversity of the people who work there, including their various backgrounds and points of view. However, the unfortunate truth is that nepotism is still prevalent in the workplace, and it controls many aspects of business operations, including recruitment, promotions, and compensation increases, amongst others. It poses a significant risk not only to the expansion of a business but also to the advancement of an individual's profession. Nepotism can be very disheartening, particularly in conditions where jobs are scarce, particularly if you see that someone else is getting a position that you believe you are qualified for. This practice can be found in virtually all organisations, both governmental and private, and it is widespread. The most significant drawback of favouritism in the workplace is that it frequently results in the exclusion of competent individuals who would have been able to make a significant contribution to the organisation's overall performance, while also providing an advantage to those who do not merit it (Labrague et al., 2017). It is critical to keep in mind that workplace nepotism primarily facilitates the appointment of candidates for positions with lower levels of education, training, and experience based on their relationships with the hiring manager, other managers, or the chief executive officer of the company (Meyer and Allen, 1990). Both developing and established nations experience a high level of nepotism (Arash & Tumer, 2008).

➤ *Favouritism*

Favouritism is one factor that contributes to workplace tension in the hospitality sector. Favouritism refers to the practice of hiring nieces, nephews, or other relatives primarily based on their kinship rather than their competence. Also, it is a form of special treatment given to particular people based on their social connections (Iqbal & Ahmad, 2020). Such actions portray partiality and unfairness, qualities that have been shown time and time again to pose a negative impact on employee outcomes. Favouritism fosters knowledge-hiding behaviour and reduces workers' psychological capital. Favouritism could be real or perceived, and either would be detrimental to the success of the firm and the well-being of its personnel. As a result, the worker might hide information that is crucial to the operation of the business (Abubakar et al., 2017; Gaskin et al., 2016).

Nepotism and cronyism are two major types of favouritism, and they are both ethical issues for businesses in Malaysia, Nigeria, and around the globe. Numerous writers have made the case that nepotism is harmful for some reasons (e.g., Bayhan, 2002; Ateş, 2005; Zler et al, 2007; Genç and Deryal, 2006; Arasl and Tümer, 2008; Ztürk, 2008). Public servants who are chosen for their family connections may not perform as well as applicants who are appropriately qualified because they lack the requisite expertise and understanding to do the job effectively. As a direct consequence of this, organisational harmony, fairness, and motivation are annihilated, and inefficiency, a dearth of training opportunities, and stagnation in professional development are also produced.

➤ *Cronyism*

Appointing someone to a public post based on a friendship or its derivatives constitutes cronyism. According to Aligica and Tarko (2014), cronyism is now classified as a relational or structural occurrence. The definition of cronyism as an interpersonal or relational occurrence is "a mutually beneficial interaction wherein party A demonstrates preference to party B due to common membership in a community of individuals at the cost of party C's comparable or greater entitlement to the prized resource" (Khatri et al., 2006, p. 62). In a nutshell, favouritism given to an individual due to their relationships with others is known as cronyism. Recruitment of close companions, friends, and close relatives without thoroughly evaluating their suitability for crucial positions. Cronyism is an economic framework "in which individuals related to the political establishment who develop and implement policies receive privileges that have significant economic value" as a structural or systemic phenomenon (Haber, 2002, p. 22). This kind of system is known as "crony capitalism." In crony capitalism, companies cultivate and profit from their connections to politicians to influence public policy in the direction of their goals (Smith & Sutter, 2012).

➤ *Meritocracy*

Meritocracy, as defined by Poocharoen and Brillantes (2013) and Imbroscio (2016), is a social system in which a person's advancement within the community is determined by their skills and accomplishments as opposed to by their position in society, familial background, or financial situation. Meritocracy, in particular, has grown in popularity as a good system in Western countries. It is closely associated with the egalitarian and capitalist ideologies that are at the heart of the "American Dream." (Sealy, 2010). According to research by So (2015) and Zhang (2015), Asia was where the idea of meritocracy first arose, suggesting that it was there before it spread to Western societies.

Meritocracy has ingrained the idea that anyone can succeed in today's society if they acquire the required skills, enabling members of low-status groups to harbour aspirations of rising to higher social, economic, and hierarchical status (Wiederkehr et al., 2015). In this way, meritocracy has been a driving force behind the upward movement that has kept society under control and quelled unhappiness. Meritocracy has become ingrained as a guiding concept in many Confucian-heavy Asian nations, including Malaysia, Singapore, Korea, and China. Meritocracy has been examined in a variety of academic sectors, including business, public administration, education, psychology, and others, to better understand the cultural and social setting in which we live.

The phrase "meritocracy" is portrayed in literature in a variety of ways. One technique is to consider meritocracy ideas as one of the philosophies that promote a status-focused system. (Major and Kaiser, 2017). In this approach, the label "status-legitimising beliefs" (SLBs) is used to characterise how the Meritocracy components of upward social mobility and hard effort are employed to understand events in ways that explain social differences. As a result, SLBs incorporate two of the fundamental criteria of the Meritocracy worldview.

Another tactic is to apply the Protestant Work Ethic (PWE; Weber, 1958). PWE symbolises the meritocracy notion that tenacity is the secret to success, which was originally emphasised as a core characteristic. Consequently, PWE conviction is a component of meritocracy. It is interesting to observe that the two conceptualizations of the "meritocracy" belief appear to be founded on identical justification-motivated logic (Kunda, 1990), which asserts that people with a low social standing are more inclined to experience unfair treatment and are additionally probable to be considered accountable due to their comparative disadvantage position (Levy et al., 2005, 2006, 2010; Major and Kaiser, 2017). The meritocratic idea has been used in private companies as well; it frequently corresponds with recruiting practices that evaluate candidates' services to the business while assessing achievement (Barbosa, 2014). S'liwa and Johansson (2014) claim that Western businesses have long used the meritocratic management style to only handle hiring, choosing, and promoting workers following meritocratic principles as opposed to the appointment and promotion of persons at random.

C. Theoretical Framework

➤ *Equity Theory*

The premise of equity theory is that when employees sense unfairness in employment practices, they become disinterested in both their employers and their positions. Employees may respond to this in a variety of ways, including demotivation, decreased effort, discontentment, or in more extreme cases, disturbance. According to the 1965 Adams' Equity Theory of Motivation, productive results and high levels of motivation are only possible when workers feel like their treatment is equitable. This concept is comparable to Maslow's hierarchy of needs and Herzberg's two sorts of motivation, intrinsic and extrinsic. In business settings, industrial psychologists frequently use equity theory to describe how a worker's motivation and their perceptions of fair or unfair treatment are related. The equity theory, according to Adams (1965), presents the idea of societal comparisons by having workers assess their personal inputs or results proportions in the context of comparisons with the contributions or results proportions of other staff members. Inputs in this case include the employee's drive and desire, as well as their time, knowledge, credentials, and experience (Carrell and Dittrich, 1978). Financial compensation, perks, bonuses, and flexible work schedules are examples of outcomes. Employees who sense inequality will attempt to lessen it by altering inputs and/or outcomes directly, engaging in a process known as cognitive distortion, or quitting the company (Carrell and Dittrich, 1978). These perceptions of injustice, or more particularly corporate justice, are perceptions of inequity. This consequently has far-reaching effects on employee productivity and performance as well as nepotism.

➤ *Ethical Theory*

Human actions should only be driven by goodwill, according to Immanuel Kant's ethical theory; the other two are not thought to be morally acceptable. No matter whether one agrees with the approach or decision, one should only be driven by a sense of obligation, according to the concept of "goodwill." (Graafland 2007, p. 176). The inference that motivation based on nepotism is not motivated by kindness is made possible by this theory. Nepotism in the business world can be referred to as business corruption, particularly if obligation ethics are used to explain the issue. The basic thesis of this statement is that a person should, under moral norms, hire friends who have relevant industrial expertise over other applicants, even if they are more qualified, or have a higher education. Nepotism, however, would be improper if one were to view this concept from the perspective of moral responsibility because one should hire a worker who is thought to be more qualified for the post.

Furthermore, according to Schlick (2008), the urge to place morality's foundation on an unshakeable basis or maybe even to eliminate the need for a foundation gives rise to the ethics of obligation. (p. 206). This theory contends that there are particular standards for the ideal candidate in terms of nepotism. Relatives should not be hired unless they satisfy the qualifications or have "absolutely firm ground" (Schlick 2008, p. 206). Otherwise, it amounts to corporate corruption and cannot be utilised to support the ethical theory known as the ethics of responsibility. The issue is that, according to the ethics of responsibility, one should follow the rules established at work and should not let personal preferences or other considerations get in the way of what they should do. Even if individuals choose to employ relatives because it is morally right to do so and because it is in line with their moral convictions, nepotism should be outlawed at all levels of authority, whether in business or politics.

D. Empirical Review

Büte (2011) looked into how nepotism affected the actions of staff of public banks operating in Ankara, Turkey, using a study sample of 243 participants. According to his research, nepotism substantially lowers organisational commitment, work satisfaction, and intent to keep staff.

Additionally, Nadeem et al. (2015) examined Pakistani telecom industry organisations. Their study also highlighted the detrimental effects of favouritism and nepotism, showing that it was common practice to fill positions based on personal preferences. Although it used to be the norm in only public organisations, this is no longer the situation. Both of the instances given were from Muslim nations, where hiring relatives through nepotism is commonplace (Abdalla et al., 1998). This is because, like other less developed nations, the state sector is the biggest employer in those nations.

Hussein and Jaafar (2023) conducted a study to explore the influence of nepotism and knowledge sharing (KS) on academic staff productivity (PAS) in Jordan. While performance has been extensively studied in corporate settings, there is a dearth of research on this topic within educational environments, particularly in developing countries where factors such as nepotism and trust have not been sufficiently examined. The primary objective of this research is to investigate how trust, nepotism, and KS impact the productivity of academic staff, while also examining the mediating role of trust in the relationship between nepotism, KS, and PAS. Drawing upon theories and previous research, the study hypothesized that trust would moderate both the positive effects of KS and trust on PAS, as well as the adverse effects of nepotism on PAS. Participants in the study were academic staff members based in Amman, Jordan's capital city. Utilizing stratified random sampling, a total of 332 responses were gathered through an online survey. Data analysis was conducted using Smart PLS.

The findings revealed that while nepotism poses a negative impact on PAS, both KS and trust had a positive influence. Furthermore, trust was found to mediate the relationship between KS and PAS. These results suggest that institutions and individuals are less effective in environments characterized by nepotism. Private sector organisations in developed nations typically perform better than those in developing countries. However, this does not preclude the possibility of observing favouritism and cronyism in those nations. On the other hand, these nations also frequently notice this phenomenon. For instance, according to surveys carried out in Canada and Denmark, Ferlazzo and Sdoia (2012) found that 6% of participants said they were working for the same companies that had previously hired both of their parents. It is important to note that Scoppa's study yielded comparable data.

According to Scoppa (2009), parents use their connections and prestige to their children's advantage in the Italian public sector. According to Scoppa (2009), those who utilised information obtained from the Survey of Household Income and Wealth (SHIW), which was done by the Bank of Italy every two years alongside samples from approximately 8,000 Italian households, kids of those working in the public sector had been more probable to obtain employment that was public-sector-related at any level of education. Except for the Trentino and Lazio regions, public sector employment is more common in Italy's southern regions, which raises the possibility that there is a connection between socioeconomic status and the frequency of nepotism.

CHAPTER THREE METHODOLOGY

A. Introduction

This area looks into and discusses the study methods, methodology, strategies, and approaches that were employed within the course of this research.

B. Research Method

The study utilised a quantitative approach. According to Aliaga and Gunderson (2000), quantitative research collects numerical data and analyses it using methods that have a mathematical foundation to understand occurrences. Statistics, numbers, and all of these concepts serve to encapsulate a component of the essence of quantitative techniques. The approach of a quantitative investigation supports the central principle of the empiricist worldview (Creswell, 2003). Quantitative research is the methodical empirical analysis of observable events that makes use of statistical, mathematical, or computational techniques.

C. Research Philosophy

The philosophical underpinnings hold that the world exists and is knowable, and that researchers can use quantitative methods to find it (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2000 in Fekede 2010). Quantitative research is connected to positivist epistemology. Neuman (2003) asserts that positivism's goal is to find out as well as validate several probabilistic causal laws that can be utilised to predict significant patterns in human behaviour. This is accomplished by a methodical approach that combines logical reasoning and empirical research on human behaviour. Continually occurring patterns, knowledge that is complimentary to those patterns, and factual truths that adhere to the laws of cause and effect are all components of social reality, according to positivism (Crotty, 1998; Neuman, 2003). Positive thinking's basic tenet is that humanity should make every effort to develop methods that are as objective as possible to produce the most accurate depictions of reality. While variables interact, shape events, and affect results, the researcher is independent of the research subject. They commonly develop and put these theories to the test in experimental studies. Its most well-known contributions include multivariate analysis and statistical prediction techniques. This philosophy holds that precise knowledge is obtained through the empirical, frequently experimental, direct observation or control of natural processes. Quantitative research is grounded in positivism, which is an epistemological tenet.

D. Research Design

In this research, a descriptive design was utilized for this research. Descriptive research studies aim to collect information to systematically describe a subject, environment, or population. Questions such as, "what," "when," "where," and "how" concerning a study problem will surely be more beneficial than "why?" This strategy considers the use of several research approaches to investigate the pertinent aspects. According to this method, the researcher just considers what has been stated or happened (Kumar, 2008). The descriptive approach can be used to explore the variables under discussion using a wide range of research methods, which encompasses quantitative data.

E. Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling was the method of sampling utilised in this study, and individuals were selected due to their familiarity with the chosen issue and the study's objectives. The population were two hundred (200) employees/participants, from two different ministries, which are; the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Finance, that is to say, 100 participants each from both ministries in Nigeria, were chosen as the sample size for this study. The Ministries of Education and Finance were selected as the study's sample due to their representation of various government sectors and their distinct roles. The research aims to collect perspectives and ideas from a diverse range of individuals within both ministries.

F. Data Collection Method

The research utilized a meticulously structured survey comprising two subsections. Initially, respondents were prompted to provide demographic information such as age, gender, education level, and occupation, serving as foundational data for subsequent analysis. The second section of the survey delineated dependent and independent variables central to the research focus, intended to probe various facets related to the inquiry topic. The questionnaire was digitized using Google Forms, offering comprehensive functionalities for robust data collection and management.

G. Data Analysis Method

Throughout this study, data underwent both descriptive and inferential statistical analyses employing various analytical methods. Initially, descriptive statistical techniques such as mean values, frequency distributions, and percentage breakdowns were utilized to provide an initial overview of the research findings. Additionally, inferential statistical methods were employed to delve deeper into the relationship and impact of selected dependent and independent variables and to test hypotheses. Specifically, the correlation coefficient method was employed to ascertain relationships between variables and validate tested hypotheses. Pearson correlation analysis, in particular, was utilized to determine the strength and direction of relationships between variable pairs. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 software was chosen for its robust capabilities in conducting descriptive and bivariate statistical analyses, generating output predictions, and identifying data clusters.

H. Ethical Consideration

Confidentiality is the practice of keeping respondents' information secret and secretive. They were treated in the strictest confidence, according to the guarantees provided to respondents. The idea of trust is covered in this component, and participants will be provided with the reassurance that neither the research's methodology nor its published findings were used to betray or exploit their trust. The importance of their voluntary involvement and their freedom to withdraw at any moment were made clear to the respondents. The respondents were explained the idea of informed consent and how it related to the questionnaires.

CHAPTER FOUR RESULT

A. Introduction

The critical examination and interpretation of the data gathered from the online survey using Google Forms are the primary topics of this section. The study's hypotheses were investigated using the collected data. To demonstrate the outcome of the study, the chapter discusses both descriptive and inferential statistics. This chapter also includes information on the respondents' demographics to the survey.

B. Reliability Statistics

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.727	30

Table 1 above describes the final survey used in the study, which consisted of 34 questions. Of these, 30 questions employed a Likert scale to measure the respondents' attitudes and opinions, while four questions were related to the socio-demographic details of the participants. After receiving 200 responses, the data was analysed using the scale and reliability features in SPSS.

The reliability measures were used to assess the dependability of the survey questions. The statistics utilised to measure the internal consistency of the items was Cronbach's alpha. The questions were deemed to be reliable, as indicated by Cronbach's alpha score of 0.727. This result proves that the survey's questions are valid and consistently measure the same concept. The commonly known internal consistency metric Cronbach's alpha was employed to conduct the dependability test.

C. Data Presentation and Analysis

This section analyses the information received from the participants' online surveys. The evaluation of the survey data is succinct, and the primary aim of this section is to communicate the findings. To portray the results in an understandable format, frequency distribution and percentages were used. The main topic of discussion will be the research conclusions and how they relate to the goals and hypotheses of the investigation.

➤ Demographic Characteristics

Table 2: Respondents Demographic Characteristics

Variables	Items	Frequency	Percentage
AGE GROUP	21-29 years	81	40.5
	30-39 years	81	40.5
	40-49 years	30	15.0
	50 years and above	8	4.0
SEX	Female	98	49.0
	Male	96	48.0
	Prefer Not Say	6	3.0
JOB LEVEL	Junior staff	32	16.0
	Management staff	29	14.5
	Middle staff	80	40.0
	Senior staff	59	29.5
EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION	BSc/ HND/ Bachelor	134	67.0
	MSc/MBA	30	15.0
	OND/ NCE	28	14.0
	Others	8	4.0

Source - SPSS Output

Fig 1: Graph Showing the Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Demographic Profile of the Survey Respondents.

➤ *Age Group*

By the above table, there were a total of 200 respondents. Among the participants, 81 were between the ages of 21 and 29 years, representing 40.5% of the overall participants. Similarly, 81 respondents were from the ages of 30 to 39 years, also making up 40.5% of the overall participants. 30 participants were between the ages of 40 to 49 years, making up 15% of the overall participants. In conclusion, 8 participants were 50 years above, representing 4% of the overall respondents. The table demonstrates that the participants are spread out through a large range of ages, with a higher percentage of them being between the ages of 21 and 29 and 30 and 39 years.

➤ *Sex*

The data in the survey outcomes shows that there was a total of 200 participants. Of the 200 participants, 98 of participants were female, representing 49% of the overall participants. Similarly, 96 of the participants were male, representing 48% of the overall participants. Moreover, 6 respondents preferred not to state their gender, accounting for 3% of the overall respondents.

This data illustrates that the survey participants are both male as well as female, with most of the participants being female. The gender distribution of the participants is a fundamental element to take into consideration when analysing the research’s discoveries. The information also describes that a small fraction of participants preferred not to disclose their gender.

➤ *Job Level*

The survey successfully captured a wide range of staff from various organisation levels of the public sector, which shows that from the 200 participants, 32 of them are junior staff, accounting for 16% of the overall respondents. Also, 29 of the participants are management workers, representing 14.5% of the overall participants. In addition, 80 of the participants are middle staff, accounting for 40%, making up the majority of the participants. In conclusion, 59 of the participants are senior staff, representing 29.5% of the total respondents. These discoveries, therefore, can help organisations to comprehend the views and opinions of their employees across different levels.

➤ *Educational Qualification*

According to the survey outcome, out of the 200 participants, 134 of them have a BSC/HND/Bachelor degree, representing 67% of the overall participants. Also, 30 of the participants have an MSC/MBA degree, representing 15% of the overall respondents. In addition, 28 of the participants have an OND/NCE degree, accounting for 14.0% of the total respondents. In conclusion, 8 of the participants have other degrees, representing 4% of the total. I deduce from these discoveries that the participant’s educational backgrounds are different, with a higher percentage of participants having gained a BSC, HND, or bachelor's degree. This information depicts that the survey was successful in covering a variety of educational backgrounds, which can help organisations understand the educational qualifications of their employees.

D. Variables

➤ Nepotism

Table 3: Respondents' View on Nepotism

S/N	NEPOTISM	SD	D	N	A	SA
Series-1	Employees always feel that they need a relative in a high-level position	0 ((0.0)	2 (1.0)	15 (7.5)	171 (85.5)	12 (6.0)
Series-2	Executives' relatives are frustrated by never really knowing whether they were appointed because of their talent or family ties	0 (0.0)	2 (1.0)	28 (14.0)	106 (53.0)	64 (32.0)
Series-3	Employees who are promoted or rewarded only because of family ties are a negative influence	0 (0.0)	3 (1.5)	21 (10.5)	93 (46.5)	83 (41.5)
Series-4	When a relative of an executive gets a job here, he/she can never live up to the expectations of the other employees	0 (0.0)	4 (2.0)	18 (9.0)	100 (50.0)	78 (39.0)
Series-5	Disagreements between family members in the organisation become business problems in organisations allowing nepotism	0 (0.0)	5 (2.5)	29 (14.5)	116 (58.0)	50 (25.0)

Source: SPSS Output

Where; SD – Slightly disagree, D – Disagree, N – Neutral, A – Agree, SA – Slightly agree.

Fig 2: Respondents' View on Nepotism

Where; SD – Slightly disagree, D – Disagree, N – Neutral, A – Agree, SA – Slightly agree

The "Respondents' view on Nepotism" data revealed that a larger fraction of the respondents, accounting for 85.5%, agree with the statement that "Employees always feel that they need a relative in a high-level position." Similarly, the majority of the respondents, accounting for 53.0%, agree with the statement "Executives' relatives are frustrated by never really knowing whether they were appointed because of their talent or family ties." Furthermore, the majority of the participants, representing 46.5%, agree with the statement "Employees who are promoted or rewarded only because of family ties are a negative influence." Similarly, a higher fraction of the participants, representing 50%, agree with the statement "When a relative of an executive gets a job here, he/she can never live up to the expectations of the other employees." Lastly, the majority of the participants, representing 58%, agree with the statement "Disagreements between family members in the organisation become business issues in organisations allowing nepotism." These findings demonstrate that the participants have a negative view of nepotism in the workplace, as they believe it can have a detrimental impact on employee morale, business operations, and organisational performance.

➤ Favouritism

Table 4: Respondents' View on Favouritism

S/N	FAVOURITISM	SD	D	N	A	SA
Series-1	Supervisors are afraid of subordinates who are related to high-level executive	0 ((0.0)	5 (2.5)	35 (17.5)	106 (53.0)	54 (27.0)
Series-2	Executives are more interested in keeping relative in good positions than they are in those employees' performance or the organisation's productivity	0 (0.0)	5 (2.5)	29 (14.5)	111 (55.5)	55 (27.5)
Series-3	Ability, knowledge and skill are of secondary importance when promoting the employees in the public service	0 (0.0)	3 (1.5)	23 (11.5)	106 (53.0)	68 (34.0)
Series-4	Organisations permitting employment of executives' relatives have a hard time attracting and retaining quality people who are not relatives	0 (0.0)	2 (1.0)	26 (13.0)	112 (56.0)	60 (30.0)
Series-5	The number of public servants who were employed due to connections is higher	0 (0.0)	5 (2.5)	21 (10.5)	103 (51.5)	71 (35.5)

Source: SPSS Output

Where; SD – Slightly disagree, D – Disagree, N – Neutral, A – Agree, SA – Slightly agree.

Fig 3: Respondents' View on Favouritism

Where; SD – Slightly disagree, D – Disagree, N – Neutral, A – Agree, SA – Slightly agree.

The "Respondents' view on Favouritism" data indicates that the majority of the participants, representing 53%, support the assertion that "Supervisors are afraid of subordinates who are related to high-level executives." Similarly, the majority of the participants, representing 55.5%, support the assertion "Executives are more interested in keeping relatives in good positions than they are in those employees' performance or the organisation's productivity." Furthermore, the majority of the participants, representing 53.0%, support the assertion "Ability, knowledge and skill are of secondary importance when promoting employees in the public service." Similarly, a higher fraction of the participants, representing 56%, agree with the sentence. Lastly, a higher fraction of the participants, representing 51.5%, support the assertion that "The number of public servants who were employed due to connections is higher". These findings demonstrate that the participants have a negative view of favouritism in the workplace, as they believe it can have a detrimental effect on staff morale, organisational performance, and the ability to attract and retain quality employees.

➤ Cronyism

Table 5: Respondents' View on Cronyism

S/N	CRONYISM	SD	D	N	A	SA
Series-1	Managers are uncomfortable with the presence of those employees with close personal ties to high-level executives	0 ((0.0)	1 (0.5)	34 (17.0)	115 (57.5)	50 (25.0)
Series-2	Friendships and relationships are considered primarily to promoting the employees	2 (1.0)	3 (1.5)	31 (15.5)	92 (46.0)	72 (36.0)
Series-3	I am careful when speaking to friends or acquaintances of executives	0 (0.0)	5 (2.5)	20 (10.0)	100 (50.0)	75 (37.5)
Series-4	Public servants frequently believe they need a friend or associate in a senior position in order to get hired and promoted.	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	28 (14.0)	102 (51.0)	70 (35.0)
Series-5	When subordinates are close friends or associates of high-level executives, supervisors are terrified of them.	0 (0.0)	2 (1.0)	30 (15.0)	109 (54.5)	59 (29.5)

Source: SPSS Output

Where; SD – Slightly Disagree, D – Disagree, N – Neutral, A – Agree, SA – Slightly Agree.

Fig 4: Respondents' View on Cronyism

Where; SD – Slightly Disagree, D – Disagree, N – Neutral, A – Agree, SA – Slightly Agree

The "Respondents' view on Cronyism" data shows that a higher fraction of the participants, accounting for 57.5%, agree with the statement that "Managers are uncomfortable with the presence of employees with close personal ties to high-level executives." Similarly, the majority of the participants, representing 46%, support the assertion that Friendships and relationships are considered primarily for promoting employees. Moreover, a higher percentage of the participants, representing 50%, agree with the statement "I am careful when speaking to friends or acquaintances of executives." Similarly, the majority of the participants, representing 51%, support the assertion "Public servants frequently believe they need a friend or associate in a senior position to get hired and promoted." Lastly, the majority of the participants, representing 54.5%, agree with the statement "When subordinates are close friends or associates of high-level executives, supervisors are terrified of them." These findings illustrate that participants have a negative perception of cronyism in the workplace, as they believe it can create a culture of fear and discomfort among employees.

➤ Productivity

Table 6: Respondents' View on Productivity

S/N	PRODUCTIVITY	SD	D	N	A	SA
Series-1	Employees absorbed through family relatives have low work performance	0 ((0.0)	1 (0.5)	32 (16.0)	112 (56.0)	55 (27.5)
Series-2	Nepotist employees hardly accomplished tasks quickly and efficiently	0 (0.0)	1 (0.5)	22 (11.0)	114 (57.0)	63 (31.5)
Series-3	Nepotist employees hardly meet up with their target	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	24 (12.0)	105 (52.5)	71 (35.5)
Series-4	Direct employees always set a high standard of task accomplishment	0 (0.0)	3 (1.5)	19 (9.5)	97 (48.5)	81 (40.5)
Series-5	Direct employees easily achieve task accomplishment	13 (6.5)	79 (39.5)	16 (8.0)	38 (19.0)	54 (27.0)

Source: SPSS Output

Where; SD – Slightly disagree, D – Disagree, N – Neutral, A – Agree, SA – Slightly agree

Fig 5: Respondents' View on Productivity

Where; SD – Slightly disagree, D – Disagree, N – Neutral, A – Agree, SA – Slightly agree.

The "Respondents' View on Productivity" data depicts that the majority of the participants, representing 56%, support the assertion that " Employees hired through family connections have low work performance." Similarly, the majority of the participants, representing 57%, agree with the statement, "Nepotistic employees hardly accomplish tasks quickly and efficiently." Moreover, the majority of the participants, representing 52.5%, agree with the statement "Nepotistic employees hardly meet up with their targets." Similarly, a higher percentage of the participants, accounting for 48.5%, agree with the statement "Direct employees always set a high standard of task accomplishment." However, the majority of the participants, representing 39.5%, disagree with the statement "When subordinates are close friends or associates of high-level executives, supervisors are terrified of them."

Therefore, these findings suggest that participants believe that nepotism can negatively impact productivity in the workplace, as employees hired through family connections may not be as efficient and effective as direct employees.

➤ Close Ties

Table 7: Respondents' View on Close Ties

S/N	CLOSE TIES	SD	D	N	A	SA
Series-1	I interact with other members of my team outside of work-related activities	0 ((0.0)	2 (1.0)	25 (12.5)	116 (58.0)	58 (29.0)
Series-2	I share personal information with my teammates	0 (0.0)	1 (0.5)	25 (12.5)	106 (53.0)	68 (34.0)
Series-3	I socialise with people outside of my close network ties	0 (0.0)	1 (0.5)	22 (11.0)	111 (55.0)	66 (33.0)
Series-4	I make efforts to cultivate stronger relationships with family and close friends	0 (0.0)	2 (1.0)	18 (9.0)	113 (56.5)	67 (33.5)
Series-5	My family and my close friend's network have helped me to achieve some goals in life	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	19 (9.5)	111 (55.5)	70 (35.0)

Source: SPSS Output

Where; SD – Slightly disagree, D – Disagree, N – Neutral, A – Agree, SA – Slightly agree.

Fig 6: Respondents' View on Close Ties
Where; SD – Slightly disagree, D – Disagree, N – Neutral, A – Agree, SA – Slightly agree.

The "Respondents' view on Close Ties" data shows that a higher fraction of the participants, accounting for 58%, agree with the statement "I interact with other members of my team outside of work-related activities." Similarly, the majority of the participants, representing 56%, agree with the sentence "I share personal information with my teammates." Also, 55%, agree with the statement "I socialise with people outside of my close network ties." Similarly, a higher percentage of the participants, representing 56.5%, agree with the statement "I make efforts to cultivate stronger relationships with family and close friends." Lastly, a higher fraction of the participants, representing 55.5%, agree with the statement "My family and my close friend's network have helped me to achieve some goals in life." These findings suggest that participants believe in the importance of close ties and social relationships in their personal and professional lives.

➤ *Effective Teamwork*

Table 8: Respondents' View on Effective Teamwork

S/N	EFFECTIVE TEAMWORK	SD	D	N	A	SA
Series-1	Close network ties are important among team members for achieving effective teamwork	0 ((0.0))	0 (0.0)	38 (19.0)	115 (57.5)	47 (23.5)
Series-2	I motivate my team with different strategies	0 (0.0)	2 (1.0)	17 (8.5)	108 (54.0)	73 (36.5)
Series-3	My teammates understand my strengths and weaknesses	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	22 (11.0)	99 (49.5)	79 (39.5)
Series-4	My teammates go above and beyond to support me	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	24 (12.0)	116 (58.0)	60 (30.0)
Series-5	I participate in team building activities often	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	21 (10.5)	99 (49.5)	80 (40.0)

Source: SPSS Output
Where; SD – Slightly disagree, D – Disagree, N – Neutral, A – Agree, SA – Slightly agree.

Fig 7: Respondents' View on Effective Teamwork
Where; SD – Slightly disagree, D – Disagree, N – Neutral, A – Agree, SA – Slightly agree.

The "Respondents' view on Effective Teamwork". data shows that a higher fraction of the respondents, accounting 57.5%, agree with the sentence "Close network ties are important among team members for achieving effective teamwork." Similarly, a higher percentage of the participants, accounting 54%, agree with the sentence "I motivate my team with different strategies." Moreover, the higher fraction of the participants, accounting 49.5%, agree with the statement "My teammates understand my strengths and weaknesses." Similarly, the higher fraction of the participants, representing 58%, agree with the statement "My teammates go above and beyond to support me." Finally, most of the participants, accounting 49.5%, agree with the statement "I participate in team building activities often." These findings suggest that participants believe in the importance of close network ties, motivation, understanding of strengths and weaknesses, and team building activities in achieving effective teamwork.

E. Hypothesis Testing

➤ Hypothesis One

- H₀: There is no significant relationship between nepotism and the productivity of public servants in the public sector in Nigeria
- H₁: There is a significant relationship between nepotism and the productivity of public servants in the public sector in Nigeria

Table 9: Result of the Correlation Coefficient Test

		NEPOTISM	PRODUCTIVITY
NEPOTISM	Pearson Correlation	1	.277**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	200	200
PRODUCTIVITY	Pearson Correlation	.277**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	200	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output

The relationship between nepotism and productivity is shown by the Pearson correlation coefficients, significance levels also, and the quantity of cases in Table 9 above. According to the premise that the data is normally distributed, the Pearson correlation coefficient represents the interrelationship between nepotism and productivity. There is a weak but positive association between nepotism and productivity, as indicated by the correlation coefficient of 0.277 between the two variables. Since each variable (nepotism or productivity) has a perfect positive linear relationship with itself, the correlation coefficients on the major diagonal are all 1.0. In the correlation table, the significance level, commonly known as the p-value, is also included. It denotes the likelihood of receiving findings as extreme as the one seen. The correlation is considered to be of low significance in this instance since the significance level, or p-value is 0.000. This shows that there is an association between nepotism and productivity, indicating that productivity may rise or fall as nepotism increases. Overall, the outcomes imply that there is an interrelationship between nepotism and productivity, but it is a weak relationship. The null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected in favour of the alternate hypothesis (H₁), which contends that nepotism and employee productivity in Nigeria's public sector are significantly correlated.

➤ Hypothesis Two

- H₀: There is no significant relationship between favouritism and public servants' productivity in Nigeria's public sector
- H₁: There is a significant relationship between favouritism and public servants' productivity in Nigeria's public sector.

Table 10: Result of the Correlation Coefficient Test

		FAVOURITISM	PRODUCTIVITY
FAVOURITISM	Pearson Correlation	1	.272**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	200	200
PRODUCTIVITY	Pearson Correlation	.272**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	200	200

** . Correlation is Significant at the 0.01 Level (2-Tailed).

Source: SPSS Output

The Pearson correlation coefficients, significance levels also, and the number of cases for the correlation between favouritism and productivity are displayed in Table 10 above. The correlation coefficient between favouritism and productivity is 0.272, which shows that there is a weak but favourable relationship between the two. The correlation table also shows the significance level, which indicates the likelihood of getting findings as extreme as the one reported. The correlation in this instance has a low level of significance, as shown by the significance level or p-value of 0.000. In other words, if favouritism rises, productivity may rise or fall, indicating that there is a straight relationship between the two. Overall, these findings indicate that there exists a connection between favouritism and productivity, but it is not a strong relationship. The null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected in favour of the alternate hypothesis (H₁), which claims that favouritism and worker productivity in Nigeria's public sector are significantly correlated.

➤ Hypothesis Three

- H₀: There is no significant relationship between cronyism and public servants' productivity in Nigeria's public sector.
- H₁: There is a significant relationship between cronyism and public servants' productivity in Nigeria's public sector.

Table 11: Result of the Correlation Coefficient Test

		CRONYISM	PRODUCTIVITY
CRONYISM	Pearson Correlation	1	.261**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	200	200
PRODUCTIVITY	Pearson Correlation	.261**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	200	200

** . Correlation is Significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output

The Pearson correlation coefficients, significance levels also, and the number of cases for the correlation between cronyism and productivity are displayed in Table 11 above. Assuming that the information is properly distributed, the Pearson correlation coefficient is a measure of the linear connection between cronyism and productivity. The correlation coefficient between cronyism and productivity is 0.261, which shows that there is a weak but favourable relationship between the two. The correlation table also shows the significance level, which indicates the likelihood of getting findings as extreme as the one reported. The correlation in this instance has a low level of significance, as shown by the significance level or p-value of 0.000. In other words, if cronyism rises, productivity may rise or fall, indicating that there is a straight relationship between the two. Overall, these findings suggest that there exists a connection between cronyism and productivity, but it is not a strong relationship. The null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected in favour of the alternate hypothesis (H₁), which claims that cronyism and worker productivity in Nigeria's public sector are significantly correlated.

➤ Hypothesis Four

- H₀: There is no significant relationship between close network ties and effective teamwork in administrative policy
- H₁: There is a significant relationship between close network ties and effective teamwork in administrative policy

Table 12: Result of the Correlation Coefficient Test

		CLOSE TIES	EFFECTIVE TEAMWORK
CLOSE TIES	Pearson Correlation	1	.281**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	200	200
EFFECTIVE TEAMWORK	Pearson Correlation	.281**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	200	200
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). Source: SPSS Output			

Pearson correlation coefficients, significance levels, and number of cases for the association between strong network linkages and successful teamwork are displayed in Table 12 above. Given that the data is assumed to be regularly distributed, the Pearson correlation coefficient serves as a measurement of the association between strong network linkages and productive teamwork. The correlation coefficient between strong network linkages and productive teamwork is 0.281, which depicts that there is only a weak positive correlation between these two factors. The chance of generating findings as extreme as the one observed is shown by the p-value, which is also presented in the correlation table. The correlation in this instance has a low level of significance, as indicated by the p-value of 0.000. This shows that there is a relationship between tight network connections and productive teams, which means that as close network connections grow, effective teamwork may or may not grow as well. Overall, these findings suggest that there exists a connection between close network ties and effective teamwork, but it is not a strong relationship. As a result, the alternate hypothesis (H1), which contends that strong network linkages and productive teamwork in administrative policy are significantly related, is accepted over the null hypothesis (H0).

CHAPTER FIVE DISCUSSION

A. Introduction

This section provides a comprehensive overview of the analysis conducted in the preceding chapters. It endeavours to identify any limitations inherent in the study, assess the implications of the research findings, and proffer recommendations based on the outcomes.

B. Summary of Analysis

- Hypothesis One: The analysis reveals a positive correlation between nepotism and productivity within Nigeria's public sector, albeit with slight significance. These findings suggest a discernible connection between productivity levels and the prevalence of nepotism, favouring the alternative hypothesis (H1) over the null hypothesis (H0).
- Hypothesis Two: Similarly, the analysis indicates a positive correlation between favouritism and productivity in Nigeria's public sector, albeit with a weak association. While a connection between favouritism and productivity is evident, its impact appears to be relatively modest, supporting the alternative hypothesis (H1) over the null hypothesis (H0).
- Hypothesis Three: The analysis suggests a tentative positive relationship between cronyism and productivity within Nigeria's public sector. These results underscore the existence of a discernible connection between cronyism and productivity levels, favouring the alternative hypothesis (H1) over the null hypothesis (H0).
- Hypothesis Four: Findings suggest a marginally favourable association between close network ties and effective teamwork in administrative policy. The data highlight a linear relationship between close network ties and effective teamwork, suggesting that as close network ties strengthen, the potential for productive teamwork also increases, supporting the alternative hypothesis (H1) over the null hypothesis (H0).

CHAPTER SIX CONCLUSION

According to the findings, there is a weak but positive connection between cronyism and worker productivity in Nigeria's public sector, that is, even while productivity may increase or decrease, cronyism increases. This shows that cronyism is just one of many elements that could have an impact on public servants' productivity in Nigeria. For the functionality of a country, the productivity of public servants from all public sectors is paramount, therefore officials should consider these findings.

According to the research, the impacts of cronyism, favouritism, and nepotism on the output of the public sector are insignificant. These actions may at first increase employee loyalty and trust, but they can also have unfavourable effects, such as a decline in meritocracy and a decline in staff motivation as a result of a feeling of unappreciation. If productivity is to be maximised in the public sector, it is crucial to find a balance between keeping good relations and making sure that procedures are fair and open. Close network ties and effective teamwork play a role in administrative policy, when individuals within an organisation get along well and build solid relationships within themselves, sharing knowledge, resources, and expertise is made possible thereby, fostering better judgement and efficient policy execution.

Additionally, by fostering productive teamwork and bolstering close network ties, organisations can create an environment that is conducive to collaboration, creativity, and ultimately the successful implementation of administrative policies.

Finally, the effect of nepotism on the productivity among public servants in Nigeria cannot be overemphasized because it undermines meritocracy, reduces job satisfaction, and demoralises the workforce and, negatively impacts the economy of the country.

A. Recommendations

This research represents an examination of the impacts of nepotism on the productivity of public servants in Nigeria's public sectors.

I recommend that further research on investigating how organisational environment and culture encourage or discourage nepotism might provide further information about its effects on productivity. Since cultural norms, legal systems, industrial characteristics, and socioeconomic factors can all affect the prevalence and impact of nepotism, it is paramount to find contextual factors that influence outcomes by comparing how nepotism affects productivity across various cultures and business sectors.

➤ *Based on the Survey Results, Several Recommendations can be Proposed Regarding the Impact of Nepotism on Productivity:*

- Implement clear and transparent hiring and promotion policies founded on merit and qualifications, rather than personal connections.
- Provide comprehensive training and development opportunities for all employees to enhance their skills and knowledge for job success.
- Cultivate a culture of fairness and transparency by offering regular feedback and recognition, fostering open communication, and encouraging collaboration among team members.
- Promote diversity and inclusion in the workplace to mitigate nepotism and foster an equitable culture.
- Institute an independent review process to ensure impartiality and fairness in hiring and promotion decisions.
- Take decisive action against instances of nepotism, including disciplinary measures or termination of involved employees.
- Offer avenues for employees to contribute feedback on organizational policies and practices, leveraging this input for continuous improvement.
- Educate employees on the adverse effects of nepotism on productivity and the significance of fair and transparent hiring and promotion procedures.
- Cultivate a positive work environment by prioritizing work-life balance, providing competitive compensation and benefits, and facilitating opportunities for career progression.
- Lead by example by demonstrating a steadfast commitment to fairness and transparency in all organizational decisions and actions.

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